

PolylexMG: A multi-word expressions database in Modern Greek

Abstract

In recent years, the study of multiword expressions has gained prominence due to the wide proliferation of digital communication. Multiword expressions are combinations of several lexical items that display some idiosyncrasy at one or several linguistic levels and they cover many linguistic phenomena. Their diverse and complex nature has led to the creation of various classifications and typologies to make possible their study and use in various applications. In this paper, we present the PolylexMG dataset aiming at the creation of a useful methodological tool for multiword expressions data in Modern Greek. To address the challenges, we opted for an integrative method, which considers all the syntactic structures of language data that are based on semantic, syntactic, and morphological properties of Greek verbal multiword expressions. The resources that form the basis of the present classification have been developed using the methodological framework of Lexicon-Grammar theory by M. Gross, based on Harri's distributional approach. The aims of this project are: (a) the development of robust and organized syntactic dictionaries; (b) the validation framework and supportive methodological tool for several lexicographic and educational implementations; (c) to provide this linguistic dataset as a useful tool for applications of natural language processing.

1. Introduction

Over the past 20 years, a remarkable emphasis has been observed towards multiword expression processing due to the expansion of virtual communicated written speech, mainly via the Internet. On the contrary, in the past, most of the multiword expressions' categories were treated as a marginal linguistic phenomenon, despite the volume of the material, and an important factor that contributed to this was the fact that the word was at the centre of linguistic research according to the principles of traditional linguistics and lexicography.

It is noteworthy that in lexicography, and specifically in the sector that is traditionally called *phraseology*, it has been understood that simple words are not always the most appropriate structural units for word description. Therefore, lexicons/dictionaries (computational or not) must include entries that are comprised of more than one word.

Within the broader study of multiword expressions, PolylexMG (<http://polylexmg.ilsp.gr/>) constitutes a lexicographic resource aiming at the development of robust and organized syntactic dictionaries, according to linguistic principles, which are constantly evolved and updated over time. Such a linguistic resource can constitute a useful methodological tool for multiword expressions (MWEs). PolylexMG consists of a linguistic corpus of about 6,000 entries of multiword verbal expressions with emphasis on fixedness.

We are grateful to the Institute of Language and Speech Processing (ILSP), the Research Center "Athena" for providing crucial methodological support and resources for the completion of this lexicographic project. The commitment of its members to advancing knowledge in the field of natural language processing has made a significant impact on the success of this project.

2. Definitions

MWEs are a class of linguistic forms spanning conventional word boundaries that are both idiosyncratic and pervasive across different languages. The structure of linguistic processing that depends on the clear distinction between words and phrases should be rethought to accommodate MWEs. The issue of MWE handling is crucial for natural language processing (NLP) applications, where it raises several challenges. Typically, fixed MWEs are identified and classified based on semantic, lexical, and morphosyntactic criteria (Gross 1982a; 1982b; 1986; Lamiroy 2003), namely: (i) *non-compositionality*: the meaning of the expression cannot be computed from the meanings of its constituents; (ii) *non-substitutability*: at least one of the expression constituents does not enter in alternations at the paradigmatic axis; (iii) *non-modifiability*: MWEs are syntactically rigid structures, in that there are constraints concerning modification, transformations, etc.

There are different names with which MWEs are called and established in the bibliography, such as the following: (a) frozen/fixed & semi-fixed expressions; (b) idioms; (c) phrases; (d) expressions; (e) phraseologisms; (f) phrasemes & semi-phrasemes; (g) formulae; (h) collocations; (i) stereotyped expressions; (j) figurative expressions. The definitions usually refer to specific criteria, semantic, lexical, syntactic, pragmatic, or to a cluster of criteria being applied each time, to understand, define, and delimit these multiword sets. We use the term *multiword expressions* as it is the most general term without implications in semantic and/or structural issues.

The different categories of MWEs (Anastassiadis-Symeonidis, Fotopoulou & Kyriacopoulou 2020, 11) are listed below:

(a) nominal MWEs: *παιδική χαρά* ‘playground’, *ψήφος εμπιστοσύνης* ‘vote of confidence’, *ταξίδι-αστραπή* ‘flying visit’;

(b) adjective MWEs: *έξω φρενών* ‘in anger’, *καθώς πρέπει* ‘proper’, *ο περιου ο λόγος* ‘for someone/something that is being discussed’;

(c) verbal MWEs: *τα φόρτωσα στον κόκορα* ‘to neglect your work’, *μου ανέβηκε το αίμα στο κεφάλι* ‘to get infuriated’, *πιάνω τον ταύρο από τα κέρατα* ‘to take the bull by the horns’, *τα πήρα στο κρανίο* ‘to flip out’;

(d) adverbial MWEs: *με λίγα λόγια* ‘in a few words’, *μετά κόπων και βασάνων* ‘painstakingly’, *κάθε λίγο και λιγάκι* ‘every once in a while’.

3. Related work

MWEs are prefabricated word sequences that represent a single semantic unit and are made up of at least two words constituting lexical clusters with specific phonological, morphological, and lexical structures with a degree of idiosyncrasy depending on the aforementioned features that become apparent both at the syntactic and semantic level (Calzolari et al. 2002; Sag et al. 2001; Baldwin & Kim 2010). They encompass various complex linguistic phenomena as they have multidimensional properties and varying degrees of compositionality (Nunberg, Sag & Wasow 1994). They have been also the focus of a wide body of research both in linguistics and NLP for some decades. As an example, we can mention the European research network PARSEME (COST Action 2013–2017; cf. Savary et al. 2015) which brought together researchers from multiple scientific fields, enabling substantial progress in modelling and processing MWEs. One of the greatest outcomes is a multilingual corpus annotated in verbal MWEs for 20 languages

relying on unique guidelines based on decision diagrams integrating precise linguistic tests (Savary et al. 2017; Ramisch et al. 2018).

The classification of Greek verbal MWEs has been defined (Fotopoulou 1993; Mini 2009) based on the lexical and syntactic configurations involved. In this classification adopted for the verbal idiomatic expressions, fixedness can be limited to only certain constituents of the sentence; a combination of fixed and non-fixed constituents in the Subject or Object position is permitted. In addition, cases in which synonym verbs are found within the same expression are encoded as different entries in the syntactic tables to establish the range of lexical options. For example, in the sentences below, fixedness relies on the relation between the verbs and the nouns that function as Objects (direct and indirect; cf. [1]) and as Subjects (cf. [2]), respectively:

- [1] δίνω/V τόπο/NP-ACC στην οργή/PP-ACC
to-give-way to anger
'to swallow one's pride/anger'
- [2] ανάβουν/V τα λαμπάκια μου/NP-NOM
are-switched-on my lights
'to become very angry'

Moreover, the typology allows for a restricted alternation of fixed elements of the expression. For example, in the MWE of [3], two alternative lemmas can be used, viz. *τάζω* and *υπόσχομαι* 'to promise':

- [3] *τάζω/υπόσχομαι/V* τον ουρανό/NP-ACC με τ' άστρα/PP-ACC
to offer/promise the sky with the stars

4. Methodology

4.1 Distributional and transformational properties

The resources that form the basis of the present classification have been developed using the methodological framework of Lexicon-Grammar (LG) theory (Gross 1975) based on Harris' Distributional Approach (Harris 1964; 1976). The latter advocates the identification of syntax with regularities of components' distributional properties leading to the first typical use of transformational mechanisms. Being a model of syntax limited to the elementary sentences of a natural language, the theory argues that the unit of meaning is not located at the level of the word, but at the level of elementary sentences of the form Subject–Verb–Object. To this end, the elementary sentence is transformed into its predicate–argument structure, and the main complements (subject, object) are separated from other complements (adjuncts) based on formal criteria.

Distributional properties associated with words, i.e., types of prepositions, and features (i.e., human, –human) attached to nouns in subject and object positions are also taken into account, resulting in a more fine-grained classification, and the creation of homogenous word classes. Finally, transformation rules as pronominalization, construed as equivalence relations between sentences, further generate equivalent structures as the equivalence relation constitutes the substitution of a word from an equivalent one.

All this information is formally encoded in the so-called Lexicon-Grammar tables. Each table is defined by a set of distinct properties (syntactic, distributional, and semantic) and includes all lexical items sharing these characteristics; entries in one table are, therefore, considered to form a homogenous class. Verbs

with more than one usage or meaning, have been treated as separate lexical items (possibly represented in different tables) and syntactic and semantic properties are assigned to each meaning thereof.

A set of features that are appropriate for the description of a syntactic category concerning grammatical (i.e., past participle form) or syntactic information (i.e., passive transformation, causative-inchoative alternation, etc.) and lexical choice (i.e., the preposition a given predicate is subcategorized for) is applied to all entries under consideration, and their linguistic validity is checked. At the intersection of a row corresponding to a lexical item and a column corresponding to a feature, we set it to (+) if it is valid or (–) if it is not.

Therefore, MWEs are treated as elementary sentences (Subject–Verb–Object), in which the formalism provides the mechanism for encoding uniform features and processing MWEs that are represented as Part-of-Speech sequences. According to the LG notation, N denotes a non-fixed nominal, whereas C signifies a fixed one; numbers are used to represent the syntactic function of fixed or non-fixed constituents. In this sense, N₀ is used to represent a non-fixed noun in the Subject position whereas, C₀ denotes a fixed Subject. Similarly, N₁, N₂, N₃, etc., along with C₁, C₂, C₃, etc. denote complements in Object position (or complements of prepositional phrases), marked also for fixedness (see Appendix 1).

However, the internal structure of the noun phrase is generally not explicitly represented; patterns depict the elementary sentence or structure subsumed by MWE classes, whereas information regarding modifiers, determiners, etc. allowed for by certain expressions is provided in the form of features or properties. *Selectional restrictions* over the non-fixed or variable elements of MWEs as well as syntactic phenomena (i.e., clitic and passive alternation, etc.) – if any – are also encoded formally. Finally, other grammatical phenomena such as agreement features (in person and number) are accounted for. The verbal MWE below comprises two fixed elements, a verb, and a noun; two variable elements, namely a preverbal pronoun in the accusative (Ppv) and a possessive pronoun (Poss) in the genitive, that modifies the fixed nominal constituent; agreement between these variable elements is mandatory.

[4] Ppv V Co Poss =:

με	πιάνουν	τα	διαόλια
me	pianun	ta	diaolia
me _{1SG.ACC}	catch. _{3PL}	the. _{PL.NOM}	devils. _{NOM.PL}
μου /	*σου /		*του Γιάννη
mu /	*su /		*tu Jani
my /	*your /		*John's devils catch me
my. _{1SG.POSS} /	*your. _{1SG.POSS} /		*of-the John. _{SG.GEN}
	'to become very angry'		

In this example, the agreement between two co-indexed elements, namely, the variable (pre-verbal) personal pronoun (Ppv) and the variable possessive pronoun (Poss) is then described as such “Ppv_i V Co Poss_i”. MWEs characterized for agreement (i.e., having this property) are marked with (+) for the relative feature.

Therefore, it becomes evident that the LG framework together with the requirement of substantial coverage leads to a uniform and consistent description of elementary sentences and the formal encoding of properties across languages in a comparable manner. An example of MWE representation following the LG framework (Fotopoulou 1993), that corresponds to the “No V Prep C₁” structure is depicted in Table 1.

Category	No=:Nhum	No=:N-hum	V	Prep	Det	C1	N1=:NPC	NoV	NoVcmN1PrepC2	PhraseVSup	PrepDetC2=Adv
GCP1	+	-	ακτινοβολώ	από	E	ευτυχία	-	+	-	-	+
GCP1	+	-	ανακατεύομαι	με	τα	πίτουρα	-	+	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αναλύομαι	σε	E	δάκρυα	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αναλύομαι	σε	E	λυγμούς	-	-	+	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αναπαύομαι	σε	Poss-o	δάφνες	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αναρριχώμαι	σε	τα	αξιώματα	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	ανατριχιάζω	από	E	ηδονή	-	+	-	-	+
GCP1	+	-	ανατριχιάζω	από	E	τρόμο	-	+	-	-	+
GCP1	+	+	ανεβαίνω	σε	την	εξουσία	-	-	+	-	-
GCP1	+	-	ανεβαίνω	σε	το	σανίδι	-	-	+	-	-
GCP1	+	-	ανεβαίνω	σε	το Adj	στερέωμα	-	+	+	-	-
GCP1	+	-	ανοίγομαι	σε	το	πέλαγος	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	-	+	ανταποκρίνομαι δεν	σε	την	πραγματικότητα	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	απομακρύνομαι	από	το αρχικό	κείμενο	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	-	+	αποσύρομαι	από	την	κυκλοφορία	-	+	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αποσύρω	από	το	μάτι	-	+	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αποσύρω	από	τη	φωτιά	-	+	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αρχίζω	από	το	μηδέν	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	ασπρίζω	από	Poss-o	κακό	-	+	-	-	+
GCP1	+	-	ασχολούμαι	με	E	τρίχες	-	-	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	αφρίζω	από	Poss-o	θυμό	-	+	-	-	+
GCP1	+	-	αφρίζω	από	Poss-o	λύσσα	-	+	-	-	+
GCP1	+	-	αφρίζω	από	Poss-o	οργή	-	+	-	-	+
GCP1	+	-	βαδίζω	σε	Poss-p	άκρες των ποδιών	+	-	-	-	-
GCP1	+	-	βαδίζω	σε	αναμμένα	κάρβουνα	-	-	-	-	-

Table 1: Extract of LG table

4.2 Classification of multiword expressions

The diverse and complex nature of multiword units has led to the creation of various taxonomies and typologies in an attempt to make their study useful in various applications. However, each classification is created for a different purpose: information extraction, educational and lexicographic uses, and NLP applications (parsing etc). Consequently, a classification that has been created for a certain application/use can be used only or mainly for this application.

To address this issue, we opted for an ‘integrative’ method, which considers all the syntactic structures of our language data, a classification that is based on semantic, syntactic and morphological properties. This method allows users to choose what they need to use on every occasion according to the aim of their task.

Table 2 and Table 3 present a syntactic typology with classifications of verbal MWEs with fixed Subject (Mini 2009) and Complement (Fotopoulou 1993) including the class in which they belong followed by the syntactic description of each category, respectively.

Class	Structure	Example (Greek)
C _o	V C _o	Το ποτήρι ξεχείλισε The glass overflowed 'my patience has been exhausted'
C _o G	VC _o N _{gen}	Δεν ιδρώνει τ' αυτί του N. It does not sweat the ear of N. 'to not care about what others tell him'
C _o Cl _(acc)	N ₁ V C _o =: Cl _(acc) VC _o	Τον φοβήθηκε το μάτι μου Him feared the eye mine 'I was scared stiff by him or his actions'
C _o Cl _(gen)	N ₁ V C _o =: Cl _(gen) VC _o	Μου σηκώνεται η τρίχα mine stands up the skin's hair 'I was disgusted, terrified, horrified, extremely displeased'
C _o C ₁	V C _o C ₁	Στάζει μέλι το στόμα μου drips honey my mouth 'I say honeyed words'
C _o P (C ₁ + N ₁)	V C _o Prep (C ₁ + N ₁)	Μπαίνει το νερό στ' αυλάκι. Enters the water in the ditch 'the process started to function in an orderly way'
C _o Cl _(gen) PC ₁	V C _o Prep C ₁ N _{2(gen)} =: Cl _(gen) V C _o Prep C ₁	Μου ανεβαίνει το αίμα στο κεφάλι To me rises the blood on the head 'I lose my temper'

Table 2: Classification of verbal MWEs with a fixed subject

Class	Structure	Example (Greek)
GC ₁ GCDETo	N _o V C ₁ N _o V Det _o C ₁	N _o τρώει κουτόχορτο N _o eats stupid-grass 'No is stupid'
GC ₁ GCDETF	N _o V C ₁ N _o V DetFC ₁	N _o ακολουθεί την πεπατημένη N _o follows the beaten (track) 'to do business as usual'
GC ₁ GCPoss	N _o V C ₁ N _o V C ₁ Poss	N _o χάνει τα λόγια του N _o loses his words 'to be speechless (with emotion)'
GCGN	N _o V (C N _{gen}) ₁	N _o δεν βγάζει τα γράμματά του N N _o does not distinguish the letters of N 'his writing is unreadable/ illegible'
GCPN	N _o V Prep (C N _(gen)) ₁	N _o ανακατεύεται στα πόδια του N N _o is mixed in the feet of N 'to meddle in one's affairs'

Class	Structure	Example (Greek)
GCGPN	$N_o V C_1 N_{2(gen)}$	N_o μου κόβει την ανάσα N_o (something) me cuts the breath 'to take one's breath away'
GC12	$N_o V N_1 C_2$	N_o δουλεύει N_1 ψιλό γαζί N_o works N_1 (one) fine stitch 'to fool with somebody'
GCP1	$N_o V Prep C_1$	N_o ψαρεύει σε θολά νερά N_o is fishing in muddy waters 'to try to make somebody reveal a secret'
GC1PN	$N_o V C_1 Prep N_2$	N_o πληρώνει/ ξοδεύει τα μαλλιά της κεφαλής του για N N_o pays/ spends the hair of his head for N 'to pay a lot of money'
GCNP2	$N_o V N_1 Prep C_2$	N_o βάζει N_1 στα αίματα N_o puts N_1 (somebody) in blood 'to provoke or lure one to do something'
GC1P2	$N_o V C_1 Prep C_2$	N_o χάνει τη γη κάτω απ' τα πόδια Poss-o N_o loses the ground under the feet 'to fall to pieces'/become emotionally upset'
GCP1P2	$N_o V Prep C_1$ Prep ($C_2 + N_2$)	N_o πετάγεται από το ένα θέμα στ' άλλο N_o jumps from one topic to another 'to jump from one topic to another'
GCP2P3	$N_o V (N_1 + C_1)$ Prep ($C_2 + N_2$) Prep ($C_3 + N_3$)	N_o υπόσχεται λαγούς με πετραχήλια σε N_3 N_o promises rabbits with stoles to N_3 (stoles = vestment for Christian clergy) 'to promise something impossible to fulfill'

Table 3: Classification of verbal MWEs with fixed complement(s)

4.3 PolylexMG dataset

The PolylexMG dataset consists of 5,635 expressions encoded in verbal MWEs, incorporating: (a) syntactic properties of the verb that occurs in the expression (valency); (b) fixed and non-fixed arguments, either in Subject or in Object position. Moreover, selectional restrictions applied to the arguments, constraints on word order, and other transformational properties like pronominalization, passive, etc., are also added and indicated in different columns. Each lexical entry is in Modern Greek, and is followed by a word-to-word translation and an idiomatic translation in English under the Methodology section.

The structural and distributional properties of each expression are coded in a (+), (-) format depending on the criteria satisfaction. Specifically, a different number of expressions per category has been compiled. Each data sample is consisting of distribution properties relevant to the corresponding category as described in Fotopoulou (1993). An indicative example of a data sample belonging to the GCo category is presented in Table 4: Number of entries per category

Category	# Of Entries
GC1 GCDET _o	412
GC1 GCDETF	455
GC1 GCPoss	555

Category	# Of Entries
GCGN	178
GCP ₁	587
GCGPN	401
GCP ₁ P ₂	102
GCPN	180
GCNP ₂	776
GC ₁ PN	850
GCP ₂ P ₃	118
GC ₁ P ₂	381
GC ₁₂	151
C _o	116
C _o G	84
C _o Cl _(acc)	55
C _o Cl _(gen)	115
C _o C ₁	41
C _o P (C ₁ + N ₁)	54
C _o Cl _(gen) PC ₁	24

Table 4: Number of entries per category

```
{
  "MWE": "ανάβουν τα πιρούνια",
  "Category": "GCo",
  "Neutral Ppv = TO": "-",
  "V": "ανάβουν",
  "Co =: Npc": "-",
  "Co=:Npl": "+",
  "Det": "τα",
  "Co": "πιρούνια",
  "Phrase VSup": "-",
  "No V C1": "-",
  "No Vcmt C1": "-",
  "active": "-",
  "Vpp": "-",
  "Permutation": "-"
}
```

Table 5: Data sample

Additionally, we compiled a secondary ‘excerpts-with-MWE-dataset’ consisting of 1,028 data samples of multiword expressions used within sentences originating from everyday speech, newspaper excerpts, blogs, and websites. Table 66 presents indicative examples of the ‘excerpts-with-MWE dataset’.

Example	MWE	Category
Για έναν μεγάλο έρωτα όχι δεν θα το παρατούσα, για έναν αληθινό έρωτα όμως... Εκεί αλλάζει το πράγμα...	Αλλάζει το πράγμα	GCo
Μέσα σε λίγα λεπτά άναψαν τα αίματα και ο διαπληκτισμός άρχισε να γίνεται όλο και πιο έντονος.	Ανάβουν τα αίματα	GCo

Example	MWE	Category
Έκπληξη στο μενού ήταν η καπνιστή μαϊμού. Οι συνδαιτυμόνες μου την υποδεχτήκανε δεόντως. Άναψαν τα πιρούνια.	Άναψαν τα πιρούνια	GCo
Ανεβαίνει το θερμόμετρο των κοινωνικών αντιδράσεων.	Ανεβαίνει το θερμόμετρο	GCo
Ανεβαίνει ο υδράργυρος στον κλάδο Υγείας μετά τις αλλαγές του μετοχικού κεφαλαίου του Ιατρικού.	Ανεβαίνει ο υδράργυρος	GCo
Ανέβηκαν οι τόνοι και απειλήθηκαν μηνύσεις για συκοφαντική δυσφήμιση κατά τη διάρκεια του Νομαρχιακού Συμβουλίου το βράδυ της Τρίτης.	Ανέβηκαν οι τόνοι	GCo
Ανοίγει η αυλαία του 61ου Φεστιβάλ των Καννών.	Ανοίγει η αυλαία	GCo
Με την αναθεώρηση του άρθρου 24 ανοίγει ο δρόμος της ανατροπής του παρόντος καθεστώτος για την προστασία των δασών.	Ανοίγει ο δρόμος	GCo
Άνοιξε ο καιρός ξαφνικά γύρω στις επτά αλλά τώρα ξανασυννεφιάζει από τα δυτικά.	Άνοιξε ο καιρός	GCo

Table 6: Indicative examples of the excerpts-with-MWE dataset

The screenshot shows the PolylexMG online repository search interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "ψάχνω". Below the search bar, there is a navigation menu with links for HOME, METHODOLOGY, PREVIEW, EXAMPLES, SEARCH, DOWNLOAD, CONTRIBUTORS, CONTACT, and a search icon. The main content area displays search results for the MWE "ψάχνω βελόνα σε το άχυρο" with the category "GC1P2". Below this, there is a "FORM" section showing a JSON object with morphological and syntactic information. Below the "FORM" section, there is an "EXAMPLE" section listing several example sentences with their corresponding categories.

Figure 1: Screenshot from PolylexMG online repository

In order to allow for dataset inspection a user interface (<http://polylexmg.ilsp.gr/>; Fotopoulou 2022) was created that allows the user to: (a) preview parts of the dataset; (b) view the examples subdataset of *excerpts-with-MWE*; (c) search and filter the MWE based on criteria. Figure 1 depicts the PolylexMG online repository and specifically the MWE search functionality.

5. Conclusion

The development of the PolylexMG dataset constitutes an attempt to contribute to the existing lexicographic databases including verbal Greek MWEs with fixed Subjects and Complements. It consists of 5,635 lexical entries which have been divided into 20 syntactic LG tables depending on their syntactic and distributional properties. This classification provides the users with the ability to use the database according to their needs, such as for lexicographic purposes, educational projects, and NLP applications due to its structure and format.

One of the main purposes of PolylexMG is to facilitate comparisons between languages and allow the construction of cross-language resources. Although PolylexMG was initially developed to serve as a means of linguistic description, its framework has proved to apply to the construction of robust computational lexicons due to the nature of the distributional theory in which it is constructed. Specifically, when multiword units come into play there should be a distinction between the various categories (noun, verb) that comprise them as well as on what grounds the classification is created along with their associated properties that define their structure.

The immediate aim is the development of robust and organized syntactic dictionaries, according to linguistic principles, to be evolved and updated over time. We intend to establish the given resource as a validation framework and supportive methodological tool for several lexicographic and educational implementations, while it is oriented towards students, linguists, teachers, and researchers of Modern Greek in general. For these reasons, the PolylexMG dataset forms part of CLARIN:EL infrastructure as a versatile technology resource to be accessed and distributed through the given open-source scientific portal. It is available via this link: <http://hdl.handle.net/11500/CLARIN-EL-0000-0000-779B-C>.

6. Future implications

Concerning future implications, the online repository aims to host additional relevant resources with the permission of its co-founders for the enrichment of the database and the implementation of various academic and research projects.

Among the corpora, we wish to incorporate are the syntactic tables including MWEs with clitics without reference with instances such as *την ακούω* (*tin akuo* ‘intoxicate oneself’), tables of verbal compound expressions, e.g., *Γιάννης κερνάει και Γιάννης πίνει* (*Giannis kernai ke Giannis pini* ‘lit. John treats and John drinks, for someone who takes care of his/her benefit although it may seem that he/she sees after the public good’).

In addition, we aim to incorporate complementary definitions and semantic features that are related to the syntactic structure of the given database. The formalistic design applied to the corpus allows for further editing and extensions in the existing lexicographic environment and its entries. PolylexMG database has already been utilized for an NLP project for word prediction among multiword expressions employing the BERT architecture model and additional extensions of these machine learning projects are yet to be conducted.

References

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Appendix

Det	Determiner of any kind
Dind	Indefinite determiner (e.g., indefinite articles)
Ddef	Definite determiner (e.g., definite articles)
Dnom	Nominal determiner
Dnum	Numeral determiner
Adj	Adjective
Modif	Modifier (e.g., adjectives, relative clauses)
Conjc	Conjunction by coordination (e.g., copulative conjunctions)
Conjs	Conjunction by subordination (e.g., subordinating conjunctions)
Prep	Preposition
Loc	Preposition that introduces complement indicating location
N, C	Non-fixed or fixed noun phrase or noun. The numerical indexes next to N or C refer to their syntactic role in the clause
No, Co	Non-fixed or fixed noun phrase or noun in the position of the subject
NI, CI	Non-fixed or fixed noun phrase or noun in the position of the first complement
N2, C2...	Non-fixed or fixed noun phrase or noun in the position of the second complement (up to three complements)
Ncoll	Noun phrase – collective (e.g., <i>classroom</i>)
Nhum	Noun phrase necessarily animate
N-hum	Noun phrase necessarily inanimate
N-nr	Noun phrase non-restrictive (i.e. animate, inanimate or clausal argument)
Nop	Noun phrase operator (e.g., ‘the fact that’)
Npc	Noun phrase indicating parts of the body
Npréd	Predicate noun (e.g., <i>courage</i>)
N(acc)	Noun in accusative case
N(gen)	Noun in genitive case
N(nom)	Noun in nominative case
P	Proposition
Pcompl	Complement clause
P(μήπως+μην)	Complement clause starting with ‘whether/if not’
Pνα	Complement clause starting with ‘to’
Pότι	Complement clause starting with the conjunction ‘that’
Pπου	Complement clause starting with a relative conjunction
Ppv	Personal pronoun (inflectional) inserted before the verb
POSS	Possessive pronoun. There may be numerical indexes like 1, 2, 3 indicating the required co-reference with a component of the sentence: Posso, Poss1, Poss2, Poss3
V	Verb
Vsup	Support verb
V-μαι	Verb in passive morphology
V-n	Noun that comes from a verb
Vop	Verb operator
Vmt	Action verb
Vcmt	Causative operator in action

Adv	Adverb
E	Empty set
Passif	Transformation of passivization
Permutation	Permutation of the sentence's components
Restructuration	Transformation of restructuring
+	Symbol in tables indicating that the property written in the headline of the column is valid for the verb
-	Symbol in tables indicating that the property written in the headline of the column is invalid for the verb
=:	Symbol used to specify the lexical or syntactic content of a structure (rewriting)
≠	Symbol connecting non-equivalent structures
=	Symbol connecting a structure to its paraphrase
<->	Symbol connecting semantically equivalent structures in a transformation